

Effective E-learning Instruction in English Language Learning: The Role of Teachers and Students

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Abstract

The paper examines Effective E-learning Instruction in English Language Learning: The Role of Teachers and Students. This study reviews literature and gives a scholarly background to the study by reviewing some contributions made by various researchers and institutions on e-learning specification and its definitions. An important part of this paper also explores role of a teacher in e-learning and how to engage students actively in e-learning environment. The major conclusion of the study is that the utilization of computers will influence the way teachers teach and students learn. The paper then recommends that researchers and practitioners need to work more on how technology could be adequately explored, in order to facilitate and foster more successful communication in e-learning classroom.

Keywords: E-learning, ICT, Teacher, Classroom and Feedback.

Introduction

In the information management systems, human agents can be considered one of the most important factors that make system run more smoothly (Trinder, 2016). In this manner, role of teachers in the e-learning environments are very important. The questions "Does the importance of teacher decrease as the technology grows?" And "What is the role of teachers in e-learning systems?" are very important to answer to estimate the productivity of the systems (Salmon, 2013). When we think about the role of the teacher in the learning environment, it could be suggested that the importance of the teacher is growing (Badia., Garcia, & Meneses, 2017). The educators' afford should be more intensive to adaptation of new learning environments should be an answer to this question. But there are some issues in order to adapt these new learning environments. These issues of adapting to the environment are related to understand the concept and the work process of these environments. For example, administrators of the institutions can understand some basic concepts of e-learning such as how it works and where and why to benefit from it. However, these decision makers will find themselves in the point of milestone to apply or not apply the concept in their institutions. More importantly, teachers also will be a point of a decision making when they need to teach any course in e-learning (or blended) (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022). Teaching is considered a very important profession as it works as a productive factory to provide the builders of a nation. It needs expertise for the justification of teaching because it is considered a tri-polar activity which involves three important stages: Input-activity- output (Trinder, 2016). The success of teaching is at the same time "a target achieved" for a learner and "success" for a teacher. Teaching English as a second language is always a difficult job as it requires knowledge, skill, innovations and dedication of the teacher. If an English teacher possesses such qualities, his efforts can become fruitful and he can achieve the objectives of his work. A teacher is a person who has learnt the teaching skills and possesses the ability to train the learners for a career. There are some teachers who are "born teachers" and they do not require too much training in teaching skill as compared to those who do not adopt teaching profession as their first choice. Both types of such teachers can gain something through training programmes but the former ones can get lot better out of teacher training programmes. There is no doubt that teacher is a tower of light who brightens the minds and produces future generation of the world (Salmon, 2013).

In the past, the traditional view about a good teacher was that a person who had rich knowledge of something. Such person was given respect and whatever he said was believed and obeyed. Now, the things have changed drastically. People have become critical and scientific minded. There is variety and vastness in every subject these days. This has given rise to the concept of specialization in pedagogy. A teacher of today has to learn different skills and knowledge of modern technology (Trinder, 2016). Teachers of English language play a pivotal role in the performance of the institution. As English teachers have to work under sensitive responsibilities, they need to know about their pedagogical objectives of the learners as well as the professional growth of themselves. They cannot gain any progress until they are aware of their multiple roles and responsibilities.

E-learning Specification and its Definitions

There is not just one way of defining e-learning, there is a number of different definitions and terms to describe the use of the technology in education: online learning, web-based learning, web-based training, e-learning. It is fundamentally defined as learning facilitated through Information and Communications Technologies (ICT), the implementation of which has recently played an important role in the field of language (Salmon, 2013). The American Society for Training and Development defines e-learning as the entire group of technology-based learning, covering a wide set of applications and processes that include computer-based learning, web-based learning, virtual classrooms and digital collaboration. It is delivered by electronic means including the internet, intranet, satellite broadcasting, audio, video, interactive television and CD ROM (Garrison & Anderson, 2013). On the contrary, Rosenberg (2008) claims that CD-ROMs and DVDs should not be classified as e-learning for their lack of networkability. Badia., Garcia, and Meneses (2017) defines e-learning as a multimedia support of an educational process with the modern Information and Communications Technologies usage. It is realised by means of a computer network and its basic task is to provide unlimited access to education without the normal constraints of classroom time and space. When carried out, the e-learning course functions as a support of the educational process. Salmon (2013) defines e-learning very simply, as an educational process with the use of Information and Communications Technology. This definition is too broad and does not reflect the basis of e-learning as a method through which an educational process is realised. In Pedagogical Dictionary (Badia., Garcia, & Meneses, 2017) e-learning is defined as the determination of different kinds of learning supported by computers, usually using modern technological means - particularly CD-ROM. Electronic learning is spread in the spheres of both distance education and corporate education. Garrison and Anderson (2013) view e-learning as learning that is facilitated online through network technologies. "E-learning is networked, online learning that takes place in a normal context and uses a range of multimedia technologies." They point out that the essential feature of e-learning extends beyond its access to information and builds on its interactive and communicative features. E-learning of the 21st century is seen as a new "ecology of learning". The authors characterise it as the technology transforming educational institutions, comprehension of teaching and learning and experience. They stress the uniqueness of e-learning as it consists in the control and responsibility for self-learning, in the art of critical thinking, in the managing of our own learning, constructing knowledge, and in the interaction, the result of which is various skills and knowledge. It supports both synchronous and asynchronous communication ranging from texts, through visuals to voice. The educational advantage is its capacity to support reflective text-based interaction, independent of time and distance. The authors speak about the so called value-add of e-learning that is created by an integrated social, cognitive and teaching environment (community of inquiry). The philosophical perspective of their comprehension reflects a constructivist view of teaching and learning. According to Fedyunina (2016), e-learning is a complex process the basis of which is a special pedagogical approach to learning. Methodology of effective e-learning should be based on the following criteria: engaging learners in the learning process, encouraging independent learning skills, developing learners' skills, and motivating learners. The scientist mentions that universities make investments in e-learning because they realise that it is borderless education, there is high demand from students, and a growing competition for students on the global education market. The potential of e-learning is seen in six key dimensions:

1. Connectivity - access to information,
2. Flexibility - learning any time, at any place,
3. Interactivity – assessment of learning can be immediate,
4. Collaboration - discussion tools supporting collaborative learning,
5. Extended opportunity - e-content reinforces and extends classroom-based learning,
6. Motivation - it can make learning fun.

E-learning is defined as learning facilitated and supported through the use of Information and Communications Technology; it occupies the central position in self-access (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022a). E-learning can be used as supporting learning for existing courses, blended learning as combination of traditional and electronic practice and fully on-line learning (Fedyunina, 2016).

Additionally, Fedyunina (2016) agrees that computers and other new technologies have become an important aspect of foreign language learning. He stresses that e-learning substantially contributes to increased affectivity of the educational process and defines e-learning as "using new multimedia technologies and the Internet to improve the quality of learning" (Fedyunina, 2016). Hronova (2011) defines e-learning in a broader sense. He views it as a new and modern concept of education and as a means by which we can educate ourselves outside of the traditional classroom setting. Nevima (2012) states that "e-learning can be characterised as electronic education which uses Information and Communications Technologies in order to increase education quality and efficiency". He points out that nowadays students can have easier access to e-

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learning through utilizing the opportunity to connect the Internet with a mobile phone. He sees e-learning as an efficient form of education because students do not lose continuity in subject-matter in case they are ill for a long time.

Another definition of e-learning refers to "learning that takes place using technology, such as the Internet, CD-ROMs and portable devices like mobile phones or MP3players" (Dudeny & Hockly, 2017). Dudeny and Hockly (2017) mention the following terms associated with e-learning that are often used interchangeably and can be confusing: online learning is learning that takes place via the Internet, and is understood here as a facet of e-learning. The next term is open learning that is connected with the degree of learners' independence and is comprehended as one aspect of distance learning. The last term is blended learning, which is a mixture of face-to-face and online learning (Akintunde & Angulu, 2021). These words are all associated with e-learning in the sense of online teaching and learning.

As we could see, the literature offers a number of definitions, multiple terms and concepts, which reflect authors' cultural, educational and institutional backgrounds. Some definitions focus on technological aspects, some more on the educational process of learning. But the focus of the means of these technologies is on students' preparation for an acquisition of the foreign language which actually helps to avoid the state of uncertainty, restraint experienced by people in a native - speaking environment (Vasbieva & Kalugina, 2016).

Role of a Teacher in E-learning

The role of a teacher depends on what the teacher wants his/her students to achieve; the teacher should be able to switch between various roles and be aware of how to carry them out (Nevima 2012)). The role of teachers changed in the history of language teaching with the change of teaching methods. As Hronova (2011) mentions some methods depend on the teacher as a source of knowledge, others see his/her role as a consultant, guide, counsellor etc. Similarly, Nevima (2012) describes different roles of teachers in relation to different teaching methods. She exemplifies the role of a teacher as a source of knowledge and a controller in Grammar-Translation Method; the role of a prompter, guide and organizer in the Direct Method; the role of a native-speaker in Audio-Lingual Method; the role of a facilitator, organizer, guide, researcher, assessor and manager in Communicative Language Teaching; and the role of a counsellor and psychologist for example in Suggestopedia. Actions of teachers reflect their attitudes and abilities and teachers present role-models which students can follow in their future use of the language. The roles stated in the CEFR include a manager (classroom management skills), a researcher (ability to engage in action research), the ability to reflect on experience, ability to handle testing, assessment and evaluation, ability to develop students' aesthetic appreciation of literature, ability to deal with individualisation within classes containing diverse learner types, ability to teach sociocultural background information (CEFR, n.d. p. 144)

In learning the language in the classroom or outside the classroom, the role a teacher plays may vary in doing one activity to another activity. When a teacher has been good in making this change, automatically s/he effectiveness as a language teacher will increase. All roles played by a teacher in language learning aim to facilitate student development so that it needs to be applied appropriately. In some of the activities teachers do in the classroom, a teacher may act as a facilitator, and many other teacher roles according to Izadinia (2015) in e-learning classroom are described below:

Teacher as Controller: In this case, the teacher is the one who served as the controller, and when the teacher acts as a controller, they are responsible in the class and also responsible for all activities that occur in the e-learning language classroom. In this case, the teacher plays a role, tells the students who need to be informed, organizes the exercises, reads loud and the other role is to give an example or show how to do something with good quality to the students (Akintunde & Angulu, 2015). Teachers who usually only perceive their work as a transfer of knowledge are usually very comfortable with the role of controller. Many students can remember teachers in their past who only gave instructions and who have inspired their students with the knowledge and charisma they have. However, not all teachers have the ability to inspire students. There are certain times for the teacher to perform his role as a controller, such as when making announcements, while restoring circumstances, while giving explanations, or when a teacher is leading question and answer in the classroom (Hronova 2011).

Teacher as Organizer: Acting as an organizer in e-learning language classroom is one of the most important roles, in which case, the teacher must organize the students as well as the very diverse activities in language learning. Usually, activities in this field are to provide information to students, telling them how to do things, varying their study groups either in pairs or groups and finally ending something and typed something that ends or finishes (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022b). This role is very important to be played by a teacher when in a timely manner. For example, when students do not understand what they should be doing, they may not benefit from the ongoing activities or from the teacher's role as an organizer. The main thing teachers pay attention to in organizing something is to get students involved and ready in all the activities they organize. Or in other words, can be said when something new will be done, teacher should make sure that the activity is interesting. In this case, a

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teacher must be creative in informing the activities that he will engage the students. Meaning that,, teachers should be able to attract student’s attention so that they can be enthusiastic in doing these new activities. When students are ready for activities, this is where teacher will guide them in doing their activities with instructions either directly or indirectly. It is also possible to conduct a demonstration against students in terms of testing their level of understanding in doing something (Vasbieva & Kalugina, 2016).

Teacher as an Assessor: One of the things students expect from their teachers is an indication that they are right or wrong when they speak the language they are learning. In this case, teachers act as assessors. This means that as a teacher, he has to offer feedback to students as they speak and correct their mistakes in using the language and assess them in a variety of ways. Students also need to know how and for what they are assessed. Teacher has to tell the students what s/he is looking for and how far they have succeeded so that they can compare their abilities from what teachers have told them. For example, when a teacher wants to judge something, he can say ‘Okay now we are going to practice the conversation in pairs, so, choose each pair, and make a conversation with the topic of travel. What I value from this conversation is the correct speech and grammar’ from the notice, students will know to which areas they should concentrate. Also, teachers need to know the problem of honesty in assessing. Students can also know whether teachers are fair in judgment or not (Wright, 2017).

Teacher as Prompter: In this case, the teacher has a role as a whisperer. For example, in an activity or in a presentation, students are silent and do not remember what to say or they ran out of vocabulary when going to say something. This is where the teacher's role as a prompter can be applied. For example, in the case above, whether the teacher let them until they remember or can find the right words typed would say something. Or the teacher gives a clue, so, they can say it or even the teacher immediately tells the word they need. In this case, also, a teacher should be wise. For example when writing, a teacher asks students the reason why they wrote it. After that, the students will give a reason but it is very difficult to get started. Teachers may provide words that can help him find answers to the teacher's questions.

Teacher as Participant: A tradition that often occurs during a discussion or a student's role play is the teacher as the organizer of the activities in the class. He can just interferes with the affairs or simply gives feedback to the students or even justifies the wrong when after the discussion is over. Basically, there are also certain times where teachers should not be teachers but participant. There are several reasons that support that teachers should sometimes act as participants. Teachers can enliven things from the inside instead of promoting or organizing from outside the group. When it goes well, students enjoy having the teacher with them, and for the teacher, participating is often more enjoyable then acting as a resource (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022a). This means that as a teacher who acts as a participant can create a lively atmosphere in the discussion rather than just as a source of information. Thus, when it succeeds students can enjoy their togetherness with the teacher, and for the teacher participation is an instant pleasure rather than a role as a source. Nevertheless, there remains the danger when a teacher acts as a participant, in which the teacher may be the master in the discussion. Therefore, the role of teachers as participant is a role that is included in the category difficult to do, meaning to avoid it he must have a strong ability and high sensitive (Baran, Correia, & Thompson, 2011).

Teacher as a Resource: In some cases, teachers do not need to apply the previously described roles. For example, when students are writing, or when they are involved in the presentation preparation that will be presented in the classroom or control them. In that case, the role of the teacher or when the teacher tries to control them, or try to encourage them, they will likely not welcome the teacher. In that case, the students need teacher as a source. Because of the possibility of students asking how to express something or ask the meaning of a word or phrase that they have not understood. Chances are they also want to know information from something in the middle of the discussion they are doing. For example from where they will get information about something that has been assigned to them, from the book or from the web. In this case, teacher’s role as a source of information is needed. When a teacher acts as a source, he must have a sense of help as well as readiness in performing this role (Wright, 2017).

Teacher as a Tutor: When students are working on a longer project, such as writing or preparing for discussion or debate, this is where a teacher acts as a tutor, working with a private or a small group, pointing them one at a time. In such situations, teachers are merging their roles as prompter and resource, and acting as tutors. Being a tutor is a very difficult role to do in a class that has a large number of students because it indirectly must have an intimate relationship with students. However, when students are working in groups or in pairs, teacher can walk around and pause with some groups or partners and offer some guidance or direction in doing what he tells them to do. However, all the groups that are formed should feel teachers’ attention as tutors and otherwise the group that will be ignored will feel sad. Teachers have to play the role of a continuous tutor even though it is difficult because with a more specific context with students, they have the right opportunity to help and encourage so that the atmosphere in the class is awakened very well as a result.

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Teacher as an observer: In the process of carrying out observations, he should be careful, not be a nuisance by hanging all their questions by being close to them. This means that in practice, teachers should not interfere with what they are doing and should not give input to them. The teacher needs to bring a notebook and pen to assess students' performance either collectively or individually. Teachers here not only observe students to provide feedback. They should also pay close attention to the success of the teaching materials and the activities they deliberately carry on in the classroom (Baran, Correia, & Thompson, 2011).

Teacher as Performer: Having learned that different teachers' acting are also different, and that they have different behaviors. It depends on what they will do. Even though, the teacher tells the students which part to play, he should also be able to describe how they can play. Therefore, in an activity where students engage in a team game, it is appropriate that teacher acts full of energy, encouragingly, clearly, and fairly.

Example:

Activity	How the teacher should perform
Team game	Energetically, encouragingly, clearly, fairly
Role-play	Clearly, encouragingly, retiringly, supportively
Teacher and reading Aloud	Commandingly, dramatically, interestingly
Whole-Class Listening	Efficiently, clearly and supportively.

Teacher as a Teaching Aid: Regardless of the roles teachers adopt in the classroom and how these roles are applied, teachers are also aids. In particular, teachers are actually very useful, using clowns or body movements, as language models, and as a provider of understandable input. According to Brown (2012), the effective role of teachers in the classroom is as a facilitator, manager, director, conductor or teacher as a source. Baran, Correia, and Thompson, (2011) state that teachers' roles are: First, at the presentation stage the teacher acts as a model, by setting the situation and modeling the new structure that students must repeat over and over again. Secondly, teachers seemed to be like a conductor of an orchestra show that directs a musician in a harmonious sound. Third, teachers are required to be talented manipulators by using questions, orders, and other clues to provoke appropriate sentences from students (Scott, 2013).

How to Engage Students Actively in E-learning Environment

The issue of making students to have a role actively in their learning and participate covers how to engage students into their learning progress. Encouraging students' learning without limit suggests putting students into the center of their learning. As the e-learning suggest a way of self-regulated activities. The active learning strategies may be very helpful because the students are responsible into their learning and they get involved into the teaching rather than just receiving simple lectures such as tutorials or presentations. Active learning strategies and how to put students in action are discussed below:

A student-centered approach is more likely a teaching methodology and instructional activities involving students in doing things and thinking about what they are doing. The learner-centered instruction attempts to engage students in activities that support knowledge constructions through media use, but which are not designed to control learning. The learners use media to investigate and to think. This type of learning activity leads to what can be described as active learning (Scott, 2013). Some of the strategies promoting active learning in language e-learning classroom are as follows:

1. Students are involved in more than listening.
2. Less emphasis is placed on transmitting information and more on developing students' skills.
3. Students are engaged in activities (e.g., reading, discussing, and writing).
4. Greater emphasis is placed on students' exploration of their own attitudes and values.

Also, the key principles of active learning suggested by Wright (2017) are as follows:

1. Purposive: the task is seen by the learner as relevant to his/her concerns;
2. Reflective: the learner reflects on the meaning of what is being learnt;
3. Negotiated: the teacher and learner negotiate the goals and methods of learning;
4. Critical: the learner appreciates different ways of interpreting learning;
5. Complex: the learning tasks reflect real life complexity;
6. Situation-driven: the learning tasks arise out of the needs of the situation;
7. Engaged: the learning activities reflect real life tasks.

Feedbacks

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Feedbacks are one of the most valuable tools in the e-learning systems because they allow teachers monitoring and improving the performance of the students in several ways. In designing of information systems, feedback also has an important role where it helps teachers to understand whether the targeted receiver (or the learner) fully got the message (Hronova 2011). According to Brown (2012) the targeted recipient should receive the message and encode it fully in order to act in the communication. On the other hand, the sender also has to be sure the message has been sent correctly by observing the recipient's interpretation which also returned to the sender (Hronova, 2011). Also, in the communication, the message sender should acts as the recipient as a result of this respond of the receiver; which is called feedback. Therefore, feedback has a potential for measuring or detecting the communication errors. Practically, those communication errors help us to provide guidance to the students if we can catch them. To find errors, the action or the objective must be known exactly. These errors help us to monitor whether there is a gap between what should be happening. On the other hand, it is a difficult process to find communication errors without getting any feedback from the students. Also, there is a great chance to learn from those communication failures because it helps learners to see their conditions and understanding about the concept. In real life situations, those failures should be used as an opportunity that goes through success. Fedyunina (2016) describes failures as opportunities with these words: "Usually, failure or success is almost entirely in the eye of the beholder... Failure is very often a misperception about the difference between what exists and goes unnoticed (such as growth and learning when we fall short of reaching a goal) and what is realized later (longer term success)". Most of the times students can make so many mistakes when they are new to the concepts and trying to discover that concept by themselves. In that case, the best thing that can be done is to show them quickly what the mistakes are and let them to have enough time and guidance to improve their performance in those parts that they had problems. In general, if a teacher gives students a space to work on their ideas, the chance to experience their mistakes teachers should give them the chance to fail. There are several learning activities that can be used that let the students to work on their ideas and have a chance of failure. In those activities the main roles of the teachers are to monitor students, catch their mistakes, let them know their mistakes and give them guidance to correct their mistakes. Discussions boards with brain storming sessions, cooperative learning, worked examples, class projects -research and in class activities in active learning are the cases where the instructor can provide a good way to let their students to have some mistakes freely and provide guidance to improve them using performance related feedbacks. In those cases, the feedback can be given immediately before waiting until the figuring that the students have some problems or they don't get the ideas in the lesson. Also, to have those immediate feedbacks, the teachers should monitor students' activity by observing or asking some questions on issues that demand clarifications.

In discussion forms, students can generate ideas freely and talk about those ideas. These discussions should start with a brain storming session where all the students can present their ideas freely. Then, they can discuss those ideas and evaluate each other's ideas. In that case, they can have further discovery in certain ideas also. The teacher also can lead those discussions to make student to generate a final goal or idea about the topic and also guide them to gain further understanding about the ideas. Similarly, in discussions, the students can also have some activities in groups where they provide feedback for one another about their work. The teacher can also monitor the groups' works by monitoring their activities regularly. If the teacher wants s/he can also has an inference to those groups' activities to correct something and give feedback and guidance (Trinder, 2016).

Active learning in the class is also a good way to provide students to engage their own learning where teacher can also have performance related feedback such as class projects and research. In active learning students are required to take action in the class by actively participating. For example they can participate in lectures by taking notes, posing questions, involving role playing or games. In those performances the teacher or the learning system can monitor the activities and can provide feedback. Other activities where students can have feedbacks are tests, inquiry, guided inquiry and scaffolding. In those activities, however the teacher cannot monitor the whole ongoing progress to give immediate constructive feedbacks. They can just give formative feedbacks according to end results of the students. For example in mastery learning tests provide some results for students to have a corrective instruction and give them chance to retest; but it is so hard to detect the exact nature of the problem such as a misunderstanding of a student in a solution part of the problem which leads to wrong results in the test (Scott, 2013).

Also, it is sometimes difficult to find good feedbacks. Especially, when the students develop a certain skill and developed it overtime. Sometimes teachers think that the learners are good enough to find their own mistakes; if they get experienced in their learning. So, in that case, to have a good help seeking and self-monitoring ability will be very helpful to those students. Before seeking any help, the learners should be aware they need help because they have a problem in their performances. According to Baran, Correia, and Thompson (2011) to detect a mistake or a problem, the learner has to have an

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understanding of the standard, compare his current level of performance according to these standards, and plan - get correct actions to fill the gap. This type of a learning also considered as a self-regulated learning where students compare their performance against a standard (Izadinia 2015). According to the several studies frequent self-evaluation produced positive results regardless of the type of goal adopted (Izadinia 2015).

Usage of e- learning systems can be very useful for those self-regulated students. In such a learning environment it is possible to have some feedback and support students learning process. In e- learning environment, self-regulated learners also can monitor their performance within, observing their actions in the system also following the feedbacks provided by the system which are called The Intelligent Tutoring System, Computer Assisted Instruction, Computer Based Instruction, Web Based System etcetera. In such an e-learning environment, students can get immediate feedbacks according to their performance within several computer managed activities such as drill /practice, problem solving, games, simulations, tutorials and online lectures. In those activities students can engage several cooperative learning opportunities to have peer feedback such as in online discussions with instant messaging or forums, online games, Wikis and online simulations. Also, the computers can give the opportunity to follow classical class activities in a local network or a web environment where a feedback mechanism can be provided by the teacher, by the system itself or mixed. These activities are virtual classes, online collaborative projects and e-portfolios.

Conclusion

E-learning has undergone great development in recent years and it is now considered to be a serious teaching method used in a number of educational institutions. In the current technology-driven environment, demand is high for new tools and learner-centered learning approaches. The utilization of computers will influence the way how teachers teach and students learn, and the teachers should make use of the Internet in ways that match the pedagogical goals.

Recommendations

Teachers have the least involvement in affective aspects of e-learning, it is then necessary to gear teacher training in the direction of facilitating positive instructor-learner relationships and building a helpful virtual classroom atmosphere. To fulfill this goal, teachers need new skills that are obviously different from those in traditional instruction. Also, researchers and practitioners need to work more on how technology could be made full use of in order to facilitate and foster more successful communication in e-learning classroom. Greater efforts are needed to supervise, monitor and track students' learning on e-learning in different ways. This is probably much more crucial than in face-to-face learning contexts.

References

- Akintunde, A. F. & Akuta, O. F. (2022a). The role of e-learning in the English Language Class: Revealing the benefits and challenges of its adoption in primary school.. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Anthropology*. 11(6), 11-20.
- Akintunde, A. F. & Akuta, O. F. (2022b). E-learning pedagogy in the English Language classroom: Emerging issues and trends. *International Journal of Educational Research and Library Science*. 11(8), 1-12.
- Akintunde, A. F. & Angulu, Y. D. (2015). The use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the teaching and learning of English Language in Nigeria. *Journal of Literature, Languages and Linguistics*, 15, 44-50.
- Akintunde, A.F, & Angulu, Y. D. (2021). Blended learning in language classroom: Benefits and impediments. In T. Ismail, S. O. Jabaar, & A. Idris (Eds.). (2021). *Emerging trends in contemporary education: A book of reading*. Kano: Faculty of Education, Yusuf Maitama Sule University: Kano, Nigeria.
- Badia, A., Garcia, C. & Meneses, J. (2017). Approaches to teaching online: Exploring factors influencing teachers in a fully online university. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 48(6), 1193-1207.
- Baran, E., Correia, A.P. & Thompson, A., (2011). Transforming online teaching practice: critical analysis of the literature on the roles and competencies of online teachers. *Distance Education*, 32(3), 421-439.
- Brown, D. (2012). *Teaching by principles: an interactive approach to language pedagogy*. USA: Prentice Hall Regents.
- Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), http://www.coe.int/t7dg4/linguistic/source/framework_en.pdf.
- Dudeny, G. & Hockly, N. (2017). *How to teach English with technology*. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Garrison, D. R. & Anderson, T. (2013). *E-learning in the 21st Century*. London:Routledge/Falmer

Effective E-Learning Instruction in English ... (Akintunde, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10020229>

- Hampel, R. & Stickler, U. (2015). New skills for new classrooms: Training tutors to teach languages online. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 18(4), 311-326.
- Hronova, J. (2011). E-learning a jeho prakticke vyuziti na ZS v CR a zemich EU. Diplomova prace, Masarykova univerzita, Fakulta pedagogicka, Brno.
- Izadinia, M. (2015). A closer look at the role of mentor teachers in shaping pre-service teachers' professional identity. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 52, 1-10.
- Nevima, J. (2012). The recommendations for e-learning towards increasing of effectiveness in LMS Moodle, efficiency and responsibility in education (ERIE, 2012), 9th International Conference Proceedings, Prague, pp. 425-434.
- Salmon, G. (2013). E-moderating: The key to teaching and learning online. London: Routledge.
- Scott, K.M. (2013). Does a university teacher need to change e-learning beliefs and practices when using a social networking site? A longitudinal case study. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 44(4), 571-580.
- Trinder, R. (2016). Blending technology and face-to-face: Advanced students' choices. *ReCALL*, 28(1), 83-102.
- Vasbieva, D.G., Birova, J. & Ocovay, J. (2016). Implementation of new teaching technologies during the action research by experienced language teachers. In *Mathematics Education* 11(8), 3089-3103.
- Wright, T. (2017). *Roles of teachers and learners*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.